

View Size of ADAS version 1

<u>ViewsADAS1.pptx</u>	<u>FA-</u>	<u>Components</u>	<u>Connectors</u>	<u>Effectors</u>	<u>Ports</u>	<u>Sum</u>	<u>FA-</u>
Slide 1	14	4	2	0	0	6	14
Slide 2	19	2	2	1	2	7	19
Slide 3	27	3	2	1	2	8	27
Slide 4	28	3	4	3	4	14	28
Slide 5	29	3	5	1	5	14	29
Slide 6	25	3	3	1	4	11	25
Slide 7	22	3	4	0	5	12	22
Slide 8	23	3	3	1	3	10	23
Slide 9	24	3	3	1	3	10	24
Slide 10	30	3	2	1	3	9	30
Slide 11	26	2	3	2	3	10	26
Slide 12	33	2	2	1	2	7	33
Slide 13	38	3	2	1	2	8	38
Slide 14	34	3	3	1	3	10	34
Slide 15	35	3	3	1	3	10	35
Slide 16	36	3	3	1	3	10	36
Slide 17	37	2	2	1	2	7	37

View Size of ADAS version 4

<u>ViewsADAS4.pptx</u>	<u>FA-</u>	<u>Components</u>	<u>Connectors</u>	<u>Effectors</u>	<u>Ports</u>	<u>Sum</u>	<u>FA-</u>
Slide 1	15	9	8	1	1	19	15
Slide 2	3	4	5	3	5	17	3
Slide 3	4	4	9	6	9	28	4
Slide 4	5	3	2	10	7	22	5
Slide 5	6	3	2	6	6	17	6
Slide 6	99	2	2	4	3	11	99
Slide 7	86	2	2	6	4	14	86
Slide 8	84	3	3	6	5	17	84
Slide 9	19	2	2	1	2	7	19
Slide 10	20	3	3	0	3	9	20
Slide 11	21	3	4	1	4	12	21
Slide 12	22	3	5	1	5	14	22
Slide 13	23	3	4	2	3	12	23
Slide 14	24	3	1	2	5	11	24
Slide 15	25	3	3	1	3	10	25
Slide 16	26	3	3	1	3	10	26
Slide 17	27	3	2	1	3	9	27
Slide 18	28	2	3	2	3	10	28
Slide 19	30	2	2	1	2	7	30
Slide 20	31	3	2	1	2	8	31
Slide 21	32	3	3	1	3	10	32
Slide 22	65	3	3	1	3	10	65
Slide 23	67	3	3	1	3	10	67
Slide 24	35	2	2	1	2	7	35
Slide 25	77	4	2	2	3	11	77
Slide 26	75	2	0	1	2	5	75